

B2-Inf at the Symposium of Czech Sociology Company

Medistella walks us through information asymmetry in the fertility industry.

Anna Dostalova and Michaela Fuller, the co-founders of Medistella and researchers of the B2-INF project, presented the project's preliminary results at the Symposium of Czech Sociology Company: Global Challenges of Medicine, which took place on 8th September in Prague. In addition, Anna held a lecture titled *"The young generation and (in)fertility: Gaps in the expectations and needs of the population and the information provided by assisted reproduction clinics."*

The ladies focused mainly on assisted reproduction technology (ART) and infertility in a psychosocial context. They pointed to the unrealistic expectations of the young generation, especially regarding the success rates of ART and the lack of information about the risks of postponing parenthood until a later age. The information on the clinics' websites was often very technically described, and there was a lack of specificity, for example, the percentage of success or prices. In addition, the information provided by ART clinics was less reliable due to the possibility of a potential secondary profit motive.

In practice, Anna and Michaela (Medistella) focused on addressing a broad audience and approaching the topic of ART easily and more understandably. In addition, they aimed to educate the young generation about the risks associated with late parenthood and provide enough information about reproductive health so the young population can make informed decisions.

During the follow-up discussion, exciting topics arose, such as gender imbalance in accessing IVF cycles funded by medical insurance programs. In the Czech Republic, for example, 3-4 cycles of ART are covered by medical insurance for women in a heterosexual couple. However, if a man has a new partner (for any reason) who has already run out of cycles in the past, the couple must undergo treatment as a self-payer. Furthermore, many surveys focus mainly on women who postpone parenthood for many social reasons (education, work, financial security, and finding a suitable partner). On the other hand, there are many women in couples where partners postpone the idea of having a child, not taking into account their reproductive age. A woman goes to a gynaecologist for preventive check-ups every year, giving her a general overview of her reproductive options. However, a man rarely visits a urologist or has sperm analysis done (unless there is an important reason). Therefore, it is necessary to educate both women and men.

There is a need for the state and the ministry of health to support educational projects and channels providing information for young people so they can learn how to prevent and take care of their reproductive health.